

Thin Layer Chromatography of Metal Ions Complexed with Anils. Part-II

R. K. UPADHYAY and V. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, N.R.E.C. College, Khurja (U.P.)

Manuscript received 18 April 1974; revised 24 July 1975; accepted 21 August 1975

***P*-Dimethylaminoanil of 4-hydroxyl 1-naphthyl glyoxal and *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-acetyl 1-naphthol acting as bidentate and monodenate ligands respectively were used for the complexation with lanthanides. The thin layer chromatographic detection and separation of the lanthanide metal ions on the silica gel layers was found quite successful. No spraying agent was used as the complex spots were self-discernible in day light.**

THE chromatographic behaviour of some anil complexes of *d*-block transitional elements was studied by Upadhyay and Bansal¹. Present communication describes the TLC separation and identification of lanthanides²⁻⁵ after being complexed with *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-hydroxyl 1-naphthyl glyoxal (A) and *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-acetyl 1-naphthol (B).

Experimental

Preparation and development of plates. Silica gel (N.C.L., Poona, India) having been freed from iron and chloride ions and mixed with starch (E. Merck, Darmstadt, G.F.R.) as binder (19:1, w/w) was used for preparing the layers of 0.10 cm thickness with a homebuilt apparatus⁶. Dry plates were loaded with aqueous acetonic solutions of metal chlorides. Plates

of size 20×15 cm and 20×5 cm were developed in rectangular jars. No spraying reagent was used for the development as the complexed species were clearly discernible in day light.

Synthesis of ligands and complexes. Both the ligands were prepared and characterised by the identical methods reported⁷ earlier.

Complexes were isolated from aqueous acetonic solutions. Solutions of the reactants containing stoichiometric amounts (ligands in slight excess) were mixed and mixture was concentrated on water bath. Crystals were washed with ether several times and dried at reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Analysis, Molar conductance and Optical density measurements. Chlorine analysis of the solid adducts

TABLE I. ANALYSIS AND MOLECULAR CONDUCTANCE OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Elemental analysis								Δ_M (Mhos)
	C(%)		H(%)		N(%)		Cl(%)		
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	
(YA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	57.74	57.58	4.33	4.29	6.74	6.95	12.79	12.72	45.00
(LaA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	54.46	54.00	4.09	4.00	6.35	6.52	12.07	12.22	50.24
(PrA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	54.34	54.80	4.08	4.09	6.34	6.54	12.04	12.30	52.18
(NdA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	54.14	54.72	4.06	3.99	6.32	6.49	11.99	12.10	54.00
(SmA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	53.77	53.82	4.03	3.98	6.27	6.44	11.91	12.00	53.80
(GdA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	53.36	53.30	4.00	3.93	6.22	6.32	11.82	12.00	51.75
(DyA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	53.05	53.29	3.98	4.03	6.19	6.29	11.75	11.86	49.36
(YB ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O)Cl	57.19	56.32	5.24	5.13	6.67	6.40	12.68	12.50	50.90
(LaB ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O)Cl	53.98	52.83	4.45	4.82	6.30	6.10	11.96	11.80	83.80
(PrB ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O)Cl	53.86	52.89	4.94	4.89	6.28	6.10	11.93	11.90	53.89
(NdB ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O)Cl	53.66	52.80	4.92	4.80	6.26	6.06	11.89	11.92	50.32
(SmB ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O)Cl	53.29	52.00	4.89	4.76	6.22	6.04	11.80	11.60	47.35
(GdB ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O)Cl	52.89	51.99	4.85	4.70	6.17	6.00	11.71	11.42	48.86
(DyB ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O)Cl	52.58	51.76	4.82	4.70	6.13	5.92	11.65	11.38	53.92

Table 2. SPOT COLOUR, λ_{max} AND R_F OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Spot colour	λ_{max} , (nm)	MeCN	Dioxane	Me ₂ CO	MeOH	EtOH	BuOH	AcOH	BuOH:AcOH (4:1, v/v)	BuOH:AcOH (3:2, v/v)	BuOH:AcOH (2:3, v/v)	BuOH:AcOH (1:4, v/v)	AcOH:H ₂ O (1:4, v/v)
A	Dark brown	450	0.46	0.12	0.11	0.76	0.76	0.87	0.68	0.73	0.85	0.81	0.73	0.20
(Y ₂ A ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	Violet	360	0.76	0.36	0.13	0.49	0.90	0.90	0.89	0.81	0.83	0.83	0.77	0.15
(LaA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	Blue	360	0.76	0.24	0.07	0.48	0.92	0.92	0.94	0.78	0.79	0.79	0.80	0.13
(PrA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	Dark Gray	400	0.30	0.15	0.12	0.81	0.38	0.70	0.78	0.80	0.74	0.88	0.80	0.42
(NdA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	Gray	370	0.35	0.12	0.10	0.84	0.42	0.84	0.75	0.77	0.72	0.83	0.83	0.39
(SmA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	Blue	430	0.32	0.16	0.10	0.81	0.80	0.77	0.73	0.74	0.73	0.87	0.85	0.35
(GdA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	Violet	465	0.30	0.11	0.21	0.49	0.77	0.90	0.93	0.82	0.60	0.84	0.83	0.28
(DyA ₂ Cl ₂)Cl	Light Gray	465	0.76	0.32	0.08	0.38	0.87	0.93	0.86	0.84	0.86	—	0.82	—
B	Pink	580	0.43	0.05	0.06	0.70	0.71	0.83	0.62	0.75	0.79	0.83	0.85	0.15
(YB ₂ Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O)Cl	Pink	480	0.22	0.05	0.09	0.43	0.42	0.07	0.85	0.22	0.43	0.64	0.74	0.00
(LaB ₂ Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O)Cl	Brown	590	0.27	0.11	0.12	0.48	0.42	0.10	0.80	0.29	0.43	0.77	0.77	0.05
(PrB ₂ Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O)Cl	Red	600	0.25	0.07	0.07	0.40	0.44	—	0.88	0.19	0.41	0.13	0.67	0.05
(NdB ₂ Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O)Cl	Orange	480	0.21	0.05	0.03	0.47	0.42	0.05	0.96	0.28	0.50	—	0.80	—
(SmB ₂ Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O)Cl	Pink	490	0.18	0.14	0.21	0.44	0.44	0.05	0.91	0.21	0.40	0.10	0.66	0.15
(GdB ₂ Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O)Cl	Red	480	0.16	0.09	0.23	0.47	0.43	0.10	0.89	0.21	0.46	0.78	0.79	0.07
(DyB ₂ Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O)Cl	Pink	480	0.23	0.09	0.09	0.54	0.42	0.06	0.87	—	0.38	0.60	0.57	0.02
Development Time	—	—	½h	2h	¾h	1½h	2h	3h	3½h	4½h	3½h	3h	2½h	1h
Room Temperature = 20°	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE 3. R_F OF COMPLEXES IN THEIR MIXTURES.

Ligand in solvent	Mixture of metal ions	Solvent
A	La (0.13) + Sm (0.35) + Pr (0.42) + Gd (0.28)	AcOH : H ₂ O (1:4, v/v)
	La (0.94) + Sm (0.73) + Pr (0.78) + Dy (0.86)	AcOH
	La (0.92) + Pr (0.38) or Nd (0.42) + Dy (0.87) + Gd (0.77)	EtOH
	La (0.92) + Sm (0.77) + Pr (0.70) + Nd (0.84)	BuOH
	La (0.79) + Dy (0.86) + Gd (0.60) + Nd (0.72)	BuOH:AcOH (3:2, v/v)
	La (0.24) + Sm (0.16) + Gd (0.11) + Y (0.36)	Dioxane
	La or Dy or Y + Gd or (0.30) Pr or (0.30) Nd (0.35)	MeCN
B	Dy (0.57) + Sm (0.66) or Pr (0.67) + Nd (0.80) + Y (0.74)	BuOH:AcOH (1:4, v/v)

Values in parentheses represent R_F of complexes.

were done following the methods suggested by Vogel⁸. Carbon, nitrogen and hydrogen analysis were done by C.D.R.I., Lucknow, conductance measurements were made with Toshniwal conductivity bridge and optical density was recorded with 'spectronic 20' spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Our early investigations⁷ have shown that *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-hydroxyl 1-naphthyl glyoxal acts as potent bidentate ligand through azomethine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen atoms while *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-acetyl 1-naphthol acts as monodentate ligand with donor center azomethine nitrogen atom. All the metal complexes were characterised by their elemental analysis (Table 1) and results suggested 1:2 (metal : ligand) interaction ratio. Molar conductance (Λ_M) values (Table 1) in alcohol indicated the 1:1 electrolytic nature of the adducts. Molecular formulae established on the basis of above studies are also noted in Table 1.

The R_F values of the metal complexes after being complexed with either of the ligands present in solvent (0.05g/100 ml) were found not appreciably different from those reported in Table 2. Various mixtures resolved in different solvents are given in Table 3. The R_F values of the mixture components were in agreement with the values reported in Table 2 and are reproducible. The maximum trailing effect was

observed in acetic acid and it was reduced when mixed with butanol. Abnormally high R_F values obtained in the mixtures of acetic acid and butanol may be attributed to the formation of azeotropic mixtures.

Quantitative Estimations

It has been quite possible to estimate the different metal components of each mixture (Table 3) by scrapping the chromatogram fragments, eluting the components and measuring the colour at λ_{max} of the complex given in Table 2.

References

1. R. K. UPADHYAY and R. R. BANSAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, in Press (1976).
2. T. B. PIEREE and R. F. FLINT, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1964, **31**, 595.
3. A. Daneels, D. L. MASSART and J. HOSTE, *J. Chromatog.*, 1965, **18**, 144.
4. H. HALZAPPEL, LE-VIET-LAN and G. WERNER, *J. Chromatog.*, 1966, **24**, 153.
5. D. L. MASSART, G. SAINTE and J. HOSTE, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1967, **52**, 229.
6. E. STAHL, "Thin layer Chromatography", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Second Ed. 1969.
7. R. K. UPADHYAY and V. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 831.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Group Ltd., London, 1969.